

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Dimethyl Malonate by Chromic Acid in Presence and in Absence of Manganous Ions

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The kinetics of the chromic acid oxidation of dimethyl malonate in acetic acid-water solutions of H_2SO_4 , $-H_3PO_4$ in the presence and in absence of manganous ions have been studied at constant ionic strength, at different temperatures in the range 303–323 K and at various $[H^+]$ in the range 0.75–1.5 mol dm^{-3} . A well defined induction period is observed. Mn^{II} ion markedly catalyses the oxidation of dimethyl malonate by chromic acid which have low activation energy. The catalysis is ascribed to the reaction,

followed by a slow oxidative break down of the Mn^{III} complex, producing free radical $HC(COOCH_3)_2$ and Mn^{II} . Catalysis by Mn^{II} reached an upper limit when the maximum concentration of complexed ion formed. The special kinetic features of uncatalysed oxidations disappear, *i.e.* uncatalysed oxidation is dependent on total $[Cr^{VI}]$ while catalysed on fraction of $[HCrO_4^-]$.

Energy, free energy and entropy of activation for uncatalysed reaction are 61.5 kJ mol^{-1} , 98.7 kJ mol^{-1} and $-117.1 J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$, and for catalysed reaction the values are 48.9, 80.7 and 104.6, respectively.

VARIOUS aspects of chromic acid oxidation of organic substrates have been studied by different workers¹⁻⁵, yet a clearcut picture of the mechanism of these oxidation has not emerged. Recently, the author⁶ has reported the oxidation of bidentate ligand, malonic acid by chromic acid and found that reaction does not proceed directly through three-electron oxidation, as was found for oxalic acids⁸. Since no work on the chromic acid oxidation of esters of malonic acid seems to have been reported in the literature, the title investigation is undertaken to understand the reactivity of intermediate states of Cr^{VI} and the role of manganous ions in such oxidations.

Experimental

Dimethyl malonate (Koch-Light) and potassium dichromates (AnalaR) were used, and other reagents were of A.R. grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and purified acetic acid⁷. Acrylonitrile was distilled before use and the fraction boiling at 77–79° collected.

Reactions were carried out in all-glass stoppered bottles, at constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$). The substrates were brought to thermostat temperature before use and then mixed in the previously thermostated reaction bottle. The ester solution was the last to be added. The reactions were studied in acetic acid-water solutions of phosphoric and sulphuric acids. The $[ester]$ and $[H^+]$ were always

much in excess over that of [chromic acid]. Ionic strength was maintained constant by adding appropriate amount of zinc sulphate and sodium sulphate solutions in variation of $[Mn^{II}]$ and $[H^+]$, respectively. Aliquots were drawn at known intervals of time and $[Cr^{VI}]$ left unreacted was estimated iodometrically, precautions being taken to minimise air-oxidation of iodide⁸.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of dimethyl malonate by chromic acid is investigated in the absence as well as in the presence of manganous ions.

In absence of manganous ions: Oxidation reaction does not start immediately and has well defined induction period which diminishes with the increase of [ester]. An increase in the $[Cr^{VI}]$ increases the rates of oxidation. The data on the effect of $[Cr^{VI}]$ on the rates of oxidation are summarised in Table 1. The ratio of rate of oxidation to $[Cr^{VI}]_{total}$ is constant, indicating the order with respect to total Cr^{VI} is one. The rate of oxidation also increases with the increase in the concentration of the ester (Table 2). A plot of $1/rate$ vs $1/[ester]$ is linear indicating the formation of intermediate complex between ester and Cr^{VI} during the oxidation. The order with respect to ester varies as $[ester]/\{1.075 + [ester]\}$. The rate of oxidation also increases with the increase of sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid

The complex formed between Cr^{VI} and enol follows slowly the abstraction of H atom with the formation of a free radical HC(COOCH₃)₂ (Step III), the later being further oxidised to H(OH)C(COOCH₃)₂. The chromic acid oxidation which involved H abstraction, all showed a kinetic dependence on the total [Cr^{VI}]^{1.8}. Cr^V formed in reaction steps (III) and (IV) rapidly reacts with another molecule of ester to produce dimethyl ester of tartaric acid, which is subsequently oxidised by chromic acid (Steps VI and VII) involving intermediates Cr^V and Cr^{IV} to produce formic acid, CO₂ and methanol, through several elementary fast steps, only when chromic acid is present in large excess.

In presence of manganous ions: The rate of oxidation of dimethyl malonate is catalysed by the addition of manganous ions in the reaction mixture (Table 4). The induction period depends upon the [Mn^{II}] and diminishes as [Mn^{II}] is increased A

limiting concentration of Mn^{II} ions is reached, thereafter, the reaction becomes of zero order in [Mn^{II}]. It indicates dealing with oxidations of 1 : 1 organic complexes of manganese. This observation is parallel to Mn^{II} catalysed oxidation of malonic acid by quinvalent vanadium^{1.8}. Constant ionic strength (μ) in the solution was maintained by replacing ZnSO₄ in place of MnSO₄.

The data on the effect of [Cr^{VI}] on the rate of catalysed reaction are summarised in Table 5. The rate is not directly proportional to total [Cr^{VI}]. This suggests that [HCrO₄⁻] is the reacting species. The equilibria involved in the aqueous solution of Cr^{VI} are^{5,14,15},

TABLE 4—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT Mn^{II} IONS CONCENTRATION

[Cr^{VI}]=0.002 mol dm⁻³, [ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, (H₂SO₄)=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [H₂PO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, CH₂COOH=50% (v/v), [MnSO₄+ZnSO₄]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=303 K, μ =2.4

[Mn ^{II}] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^5$ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.0	0.37
0.001	0.76
0.002	1.16
0.003	1.52
0.005	2.25
0.01	3.78
0.02	7.30
0.03	9.50
0.05	13.5
0.10	15.4
0.15	15.2
0.20	15.3

* ZnSO₄ was used to replace MnSO₄ in maintaining constant ionic strength.

transient pink colour is also observed during the course of oxidation, indicating the formation of higher states of manganese as intermediates. Manganous ions in the solution of constant ionic strength (μ) follow first order kinetics until a

The predominant species of Cr^{VI} in 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ solutions under the experimental conditions are HCrO₄⁻ and Cr₂O₇²⁻ while H₂CrO₄ and CrO₄²⁻ are present in negligible amounts⁵. The concentration of HCrO₄⁻ for each initial gross [Cr^{VI}] was calculated using equilibrium equation (5). The value of K_{e,3}=41.67 dm³ mol⁻¹ is estimated from the work of Best *et al.*¹⁶. A plot of log (rate) vs log [HCrO₄⁻] is a straight line, with a slope approximately equal to 2/3. Thus, the order with respect to [HCrO₄⁻] is less than unity. A plot of 1/rate vs 1/[HCrO₄⁻] is also a straight line and the rate can be well represented by 2.439 [HCrO₄⁻]/{1+0.043 9 [HCrO₄⁻]}. There is no significant effect on the rate of oxidation by adding Cr^{III} ions externally upto 0.08 mol dm⁻³ in the reaction mixture.

The rate of oxidation for catalysed reaction increases with the increase in the ester concentration (Table 6) and a plot of 1/rate vs 1/[ester] is a straight line which does not pass through origin. This indicates the complex formation probably between ester and Mn^{II}, prior to the rate determining step of oxidation. Here also similar to the uncatalysed oxidation, the induction period depends

TABLE 5—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT CHROMIC ACID CONCENTRATION FOR CATALYSED REACTION

[ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [H₂PO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, CH₂COOH=50% (v/v), [Mn^{II}]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=303 K

$\times 10^{-3}$ [Cr ^{VI}] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^5$ [HCrO ₄ ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^5$ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ Found	$\times 10^5$ Rate [HCrO ₄ ⁻] ^{2/3}	$\times 10^5$ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ Calcd.*
4.0	3.18	7.24	3.35	6.81
7.0	4.95	9.87	3.40	9.92
10.0	6.40	11.5	3.34	12.19
15.0	8.70	15.7	3.71	15.35
20.0	10.61	18.2	3.67	17.65
30.0	18.90	21.0	3.64	21.1

* Calcd. from $\times 10^5$ rate=2.44 [HCrO₄⁻]/{1+43.9[HCrO₄⁻]}

TABLE 6—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT ESTER CONCENTRATION FOR CATALYSED REACTION

[CrVI]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [H₃PO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, CH₃COOH=50% (v/v), [MnII]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=308 K

[ester] mol dm ⁻³	Ind. period min	× 10 ⁵ Rate, mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	
		Found	Calcd.
0.080	10	3.72	3.41
0.115	10	4.84	4.67
0.150	10	5.88	5.83
0.175	9	6.20	6.60
0.200	9	7.24	7.03
0.250	8	8.24	8.66
0.285	8	8.60	9.31
0.345	6	11.00	10.83

* Calcd. from × 10⁵ rate = 31.75 [ester]¹ / {0.667 + [ester]}.

upon the ester concentration and diminishes with its increase. Increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid increases the rate of oxidation and the rate is proportional to [H⁺]². The constant ionic strength was kept by adding appropriate quantity of sodium sulphate solution (Table 7). If

TABLE 7—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION

[CrVI]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [H₃PO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, CH₃COOH=50%, [MnII]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=303 K, [H₂SO₄ + Na₂SO₄]=1.5 mol dm⁻³

[H ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	× 10 ⁵ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	
	without Na ₂ SO ₄	with Na ₂ SO ₄
1.50	12.7	12.7
1.25	9.2	8.6
1.00	7.2	6.5
0.75	5.8	4.8

reaction is performed in absence of phosphoric acid, it is very slow. Rate of oxidation increases with the increase in the concentration of phosphoric acid (Table 8). This suggests that HOCrO₂-OSO₃H is

TABLE 8—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT PHOSPHORIC ACID OXIDATION

[CrVI]=0.004 dm⁻³, [ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, CH₃COOH=40% (v/v), [MnII]=0.0125 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=303 K

[H ₃ PO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	× 10 ⁵ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.0	1.64
0.384	2.73
0.769	4.56
1.154	8.98

less reactive than HOCrO₂-OPO₃H which are formed due to the reaction,

The increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the solvent mixture increases the rate of oxidation (Table 9). The log (rate) increases linearly with

TABLE 9—OXIDATION RATES AT DIFFERENT ACETIC ACID PROPORTIONS

[CrVI]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [H₃PO₄]=1.154 mol dm⁻³, [MnII]=0.0125 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=305 K

CH ₃ COOH % (v/v)	× 10 ⁵ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	5 + log (rate) (% of CH ₃ COOH)
40	8.98	0.0238
35	6.26	0.0277
30	4.6	0.0221
20	2.74	0.0218
15	2.18	0.0225

increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the mixture. The increase in the rate with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid may be attributed to the increased protonation before reaction in a solvent of low dielectric constant^{18,19}. Another explanation for increased rate of oxidation with increased proportion of acetic acid in the solvent may be the formation of acetyl chromic acid CH₃COOCrO₂OH or its conjugate acid CH₃COOCrO₂OH₂⁺ in acetic acid medium which are more powerful oxidising agents^{20,21} compared to chromic acid. Polymerisation of monomer acrylonitrile in the presence of manganous ions in the reaction mixture also indicates the free radical formation during the course of reaction.

The effect of temperature on the reaction rate for catalysed reaction is summarised in Table 10.

TABLE 10—TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON RATE OF OXIDATION FOR CATALYSED REACTION AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[CrVI]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [ester]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [H₃PO₄]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [MnII]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, CH₃COOH=50% (v/v)

Temp. K	× 10 ⁵ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (Total)	× 10 ⁵ Rate mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (Catalysed)	k [*] s ⁻¹
303	7.28	6.5	0.117
313	14.1	12.6	0.228
318	19.6	17.4	0.314
321	21.9	18.8	0.319
327	30.4	26.1	0.471

ΔE_a=48.9 ± 2.1 kJ mol⁻¹, p_Z=3.1 × 10⁷ s⁻¹, ΔS[‡]=104.6 ± 4.2 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, ΔF[‡]=80.7 ± 4.2 kJ mol⁻¹.

* Specific rate constant, corrected for uncatalysed path.

The energy of activation for the catalysed reaction after correcting for uncatalysed reaction path is found to be 48.9 kJ mol⁻¹. Hence, the manganous catalysed reaction has lower energy of activation than that of uncatalysed one (Tables 3 and 10). The entropy of activation and free energy of activation are 104.6 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 80.7 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The following mechanism (Scheme 2)

is proposed to account for the experimental results for catalytic oxidation of dimethyl malonate.

and/or

where, $k'_6 > k'_5$

Scheme 2

Equilibrium reaction (IX) represents the formation of 1 : 1 chelated complex of Mn^{II} and enol form of the ester. This chelated complex of Mn^{II} is oxidised by HCrO₄⁻ to produce the corresponding complex of Mn^{III}. The Mn^{III} complex decomposes by a slow one-electron inner-sphere transition to give free radical HĊ(COOCH₃)₂ and Mn^{II}. The free radical so formed is further oxidised by Cr^{VI} and/or Mn^{III} to first intermediate product H(OH)C(COOCH₃)₂ as shown by steps (XIV) and (XV). Cr^V generated in steps (XI) and (XIV) is highly reactive and is reduced to Cr^{III} by dimethyl malonate. In large excess of chromic acid, first intermediate product H(OH)C(COOCH₃)₂ is further oxidised to formic acid, CO₂ and methanol. Mechanism shown in Scheme 2 accords with our kinetic findings. Reaction (XI) is preferred over following reaction (XVI),

because redox potential of Mn^{III} enol/Mn^{II} enol is decisively lower than that of Mn^{III}_{aq}/Mn^{II}_{aq} couple.

Catalysis by Mn^{II} ions would of course reach an upper limit when maximum concentration of complexed ion has been formed. The maximum reached in the oxidation of dimethyl malonate (Table 4) might be explained in this way.

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